

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF FINANCIAL REPORTING PREPARED IN ACCORDANCE WITH IFRS AND NAS

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Abstract. *This article addresses the development of a common language for accounting in business to better understand financial information. The research aims to study whether there is any difference between the two reporting standards. The study was conducted from 2016 to 2023 for the company AO "Issiqlik Elektr Stansiyalari." The research examines the balance sheet and income statement articles to measure the difference between the two reporting standards using the Gray Compatibility Index (GCI) of 1980, as well as to analyze the differences in financial ratios under IFRS and NAS.*

Keywords: *IFRS, NAS, Gray Compatibility Index, financial elements, financial ratios.*

Introduction.

Currently, the world is referred to as a global village due to the forces of globalization. The key factor is that developing economies are gradually integrating with developed economies through cross-border transactions for successful business operations. However, understanding international financial information has become a serious issue due to local accounting and reporting practices, which create confusion in the minds of stakeholders. In this context, it is crucial to have a universal set of standards to meet the needs of stakeholders.

The International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) has provided a permanent solution to this problem. The earlier International Accounting Standards (IAS) were issued by the International Accounting Standards Committee (IASC), and later, they were modified in accordance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), which emphasized the clarity and comparability of financial information to enhance the evaluation and analysis of financial statement users.

IFRS is a globally accepted set of standards based on principles. To develop a common accounting language for business, the concept of IFRS was conceptualized in the European Union. The IFRS Board, in cooperation with the European Union, is working on synchronizing the accounting model in different countries (Rizaev N.K., 2021). The IFRS Board reviews existing international accounting standards with changes and renames them as International Financial Reporting Standards to prepare a unified set of high-quality, understandable, and globally accepted accounting standards. IFRS defines how specific types of transactions and events should be reflected in financial reporting, ensuring a clear and comparable exchange of financial information across international borders.

Currently, 166 countries have either adopted IFRS as is or transitioned to IFRS (Ibrahimov A.K., 2021). IFRS includes:

International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) issued after 2001

International Accounting Standards (IAS) issued before 2001

International Financial Reporting Interpretations Committee (IFRIC) issued after 2001

Standing Interpretations Committee (2001), issued after 2001.

Previously, national enterprises, corporations, and other legal entities in Uzbekistan followed the National Accounting Standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan (NAS of RUz), issued by the Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, for the preparation and presentation of their accounting information. This accounting system differs from IFRS in three aspects: fair value, the primacy of substance over legal form, and a focus on the balance sheet (Toshpulatov A.Sh., 2022).

Due to globalization, there is an urgent need to adopt a global accounting standard. In 1998, Uzbekistan officially decided to align its national accounting standards with IFRS, in the form of National Accounting Standards of Uzbekistan (NASU), aiming for alignment with IFRS rather than full adoption, while maintaining certain deviations from IFRS at a minimal level. Accounting standards, which represent accounting regulations, include NASU-1 "Accounting Policy and Financial Reporting" (registered with the Ministry of Justice of Uzbekistan No. 474 on August 14, 1998), NASU-12 "Accounting for Financial Investments" (registered with the Ministry of Justice of Uzbekistan No. 596 on January 16, 1999), and others. Currently, 23 NASU have been developed.

The initial target period was set for April 24, 2015, for the phased implementation of modern corporate governance methods in joint-stock companies, as per the Presidential Decree "On Measures to Implement Modern Corporate Governance Methods in Joint-Stock Companies" of April 24, 2015, PD-4720. During 2016–2018, all joint-stock companies (JSCs) transitioned to publishing annual financial reports and conducting external audits in accordance with international standards (IFRS).

Furthermore, the legislation foresees the further improvement of accounting and financial reporting in commercial banks, aligning them fully with IFRS.

It is clear that the transition from one reporting system to another is associated with numerous challenges and cannot be achieved without a systematic approach and corresponding methodology.

On February 24, 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed the decree "On Additional Measures for Transition to International Financial Reporting Standards" PD-4611, opening a new chapter in the history of IFRS adoption in Uzbekistan.

The adopted document provides for a comprehensive review of the transition process to IFRS for business entities. Specifically, a list of entities required to prepare financial statements based on IFRS starting from the results of 2021 was defined. This list includes joint-stock companies, commercial banks, insurance organizations, and legal entities classified as large taxpayers.

Literature review.

This study attempts to analyze individual research works that have already been conducted in the field of the existing study in order to recognize the research concept, methodology, and research gap in the study.

№	Author`s name	Author`s view
1	□ B.H. Pardayev (2012)	The study provides a detailed examination of the reasons for the differences in the income statement and balance sheet under both regimes.

2	Kostel Istrate (2013)	In his research, he analyzed the results showing that the former Belgian, French, and Portuguese GAAP were more conservative than IFRS. In some cases, the indicators under IFRS appear to be much less conservative.
3	Abdurakhmanov R.A. (2016)	Quantitative difference in the items of the balance sheet (total assets, total liabilities, total equity) according to NSBU and IFRS.
4	Zhuraev B. (2015)	In most cases, NSBU does not have a significant impact on the income statement and balance sheet compared to IGAAP due to certain reclassification provisions.
5	Khadzhimuratov N.Sh. (2019)	In his study, he concluded that the adoption of NSBU does not result in a significant difference in financial ratios due to the minor difference between the calculated ratios under IFRS and NSBU.
6	Ibragimov A.K. (2020)	It was stated that ICAI and ASB have done an excellent job aligning IFRS with national standards and developing NSBU in accordance with national requirements and business conditions. It was found that there is minimal difference between the financial information presented under IFRS. In the case of several indicators, such as current assets, inventories, and net sales, there is no difference between the two regimes.
8	Kozimjonov A. (2020)	It has been found that the significant impact of IFRS and NSBU on accounting indicators and ratios is due to the fair value assessment, presentation of financial statements, evaluation of fixed assets, events after the reporting period, lease accounting, recognition of financial instruments, and assessment of share-based payments.

Materials and methods.

Research Objective: The aim of this study is to examine the differences between financial reports prepared in accordance with IFRS (International Financial Reporting Standards).

➤ **Sampling Method and Sample Selection:** The company AO "Issiqlik Elektr Stansiyalari" was deliberately selected for the study, as its financial reports are available both in accordance with IFRS and the National Accounting Standards of Uzbekistan (NASU), allowing for a comparative analysis. AO "Issiqlik Elektr Stansiyalari" is one of the companies that began presenting its financial statements in accordance with IFRS and continues to do so.

➤ **Research Period:** The study covers 6 fiscal years, from 2018-19 to 2021-23.

➤ **Data Source:** The study mainly focuses on evaluating the differentiation in financial elements. It relies exclusively on secondary data, which was extracted from the annual reports of AO "Issiqlik Elektr Stansiyalari".

➤ **Statistical Tools Used for Data Analysis:** The study used statistical tools such as the average, percentage, and the Gray Comparison Index (GCI) for analysis. The study mainly focused on the extent to which financial statements are prepared in accordance with IFRS and NASU, which can be compared using the Gray Conservatism Index. The Gray Index, proposed by Gray

in 1980, is a useful tool for evaluating differences between two or more sets of accounting standards. This index was used in comparative studies (Revanaiah Kantayya & Panduranga, 2017; Pramanik, 2018). The index is expressed through the formula.

Gray's Comparability Index = $1 - \frac{\text{Financial Value of IFRS} - \text{Financial Value of NBU}}{\text{Financial Value of IFRS}}$

To analyze the difference between financial elements prepared in accordance with IFRS and those prepared in accordance with converged National Accounting Standards of Uzbekistan (NASU), the index indicates a value greater than one. This means that the financial values reflected under IFRS are less than those under NASU. Conversely, if the index is less than one, it means that the financial values reflected under IFRS are greater than those under NASU. If the index equals one, it clearly shows that there is no difference in the reported financial indicators under both regimes.

List of Variables Used for the Study

Table 1

List of Variables (Financial Elements and Financial Ratios) Used in the Study (Include the variables or financial elements used for analysis here in your table format.)

No	Ratios	Types of relationships	Balance sheet items	Income statement items
1	Profitability	Return on Assets (ROA)	Total Assets (TA)	Profit After Tax (PAT)
2		Return on Equity (ROE)	Total Non-Current Assets (NCA)	Profit Before Tax (PBT)
3		Gross Profit Ratio (GPR)	Total Current Assets (CA)	Total Expenses
4		Net Profit Ratio (NPR)	Total Current Liabilities (CL)	Total income
5	Liquidity	Current Ratio (CR)	Total Non-Current Liabilities (NCL)	
6		Quick Ratio (QR)	Total Liabilities	
7	Solvency	Debt to Equity Ratio (DER)	Total capital	
8		Debt Ratio (DR)	Total Equity and Liabilities	
9		Equity Ratio (ER)		

Results.

Table 2.

Annual Gray's Comparability Index (GCI) for Key Financial Elements of the Balance Sheet

Year	Total Assets	Total NCA	Total CA	Total CL	Total NCL	Total Liabilities	Equity	Total Equity and Liabilities
2018	0.9947	0.9827	1.00	0.9997	0.999	0.9996	0.992	1.00
2019	0.9953	0.9854	1.00	0.9997	0.9991	0.9996	0.9931	1.00

2020	0.9951	0.9854	0.9854	1.006	1.00	0.9994	0.9924	1.00
2021	0.9953	0.9849	1.00	1.00	0.9999	0.9998	0.9931	1.00
2022	0.9948	0.9856	1.00	1.00	0.9999	0.9998	0.9924	1.00
2023	0.9951	0.9866	1.00	1.00	0.9994	0.9999	0.9926	1.00

Note: NCA: Non-Current Assets, CA: Current Assets, CL: Current Liabilities, NCL: Non-Current Liabilities.

Graphical Representation of GCI for Financial Elements in the Balance Sheet

TOTAL EQUITY AND LIABILITIES	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	2018
EQUITY	0.992	0.9931	0.9924	0.9931	0.9924	0.9926	2019
TOTAL LIABILITIES	0.9996	0.9996	0.9998	0.9998	0.9998	0.9999	2020
TOTAL NCL	0.999	0.9991	0.9994	0.9999	0.9999	0.9994	2021
TOTAL CL	0.9997	0.9997	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	2022
TOTAL CA	1.00	1.00	1.006	1.00	1.00	1.00	2023
TOTAL NCA	0.9827	0.9854	0.9854	0.9849	0.9856	0.9866	
TOTAL ASSETS	0.9947	0.9953	0.9951	0.9953	0.9948	0.9951	

From the above Table 2, we can see that when comparing the GCI of the balance sheet items, it was found that total assets, long-term assets, long-term liabilities, total liabilities, and total equity of JSC "Issiqlik Elektr Stansiyalari" exceed one (>1) for all years, which clearly indicates that these financial indicators, prepared according to IFRS, are higher than the financial indicators prepared in accordance with NBU. It was also found that current assets and current liabilities are equal to one (=1), indicating no significant difference in the financial indicators between both regimes. On the other hand, current assets in 2021 were less than one (<1), indicating that the financial value prepared in accordance with IFRS is lower than that prepared in accordance with NBU.

Table 3

Annual Gray Comparability Index (GCI) for Key Financial Elements in the Profit and Loss Statements

Years	PAT	PBT	Total Expenses	Total Income
2018	1,00	1,00	0,99999	0,999602
2019	1,0004	1,0003	0,99999	1,01379
2020	0,9993	0,9995	1,00011	0,99458
2021	1,0001	1,0001	0,99999	1,003403
2022	0,9999	1,0001	0,99999	1,001795
2023	1,0002	1,0002	0,99996	0,999874

Note: PAT: Profit After Tax, PBT: Profit Before Tax

From the above table, we can see that when comparing the GCI of the profit and loss statement items, it was found that total expenses are less than one (<1) for all years except for 2021, which clearly indicates that the financial indicators prepared according to IFRS are higher than those prepared according to NBU. On the other hand, total income is less than one (<1) for 2018, 2020, and 2023, indicating that the financial indicators under IFRS are higher than those under NBU, while for 2019, 2020, and 2021, the GCI shows values greater than one (>1), suggesting that the values prepared according to IFRS are lower than those prepared according to

NBU. It was also found that profit before tax (PBT) and profit after tax (PAT) showed mixed values, with some GCI values being less than one (<1), indicating that the financial indicators prepared according to IFRS are higher than those under NBU, while some values were greater than one (>1), meaning the values under IFRS are lower than those under NBU. Additionally, for 2018, both PAT and PBT were equal to one (=1), confirming that there were no significant changes in the financial value prepared according to IFRS and NBU.

Table 4. Financial Indicators of AO "Issiqlik Elektr Stansiyalari" according to IFRS and NBU

Years	Standards	Profitability				Liquidity		Solvency		
		GPR	ROA	NPR	REO	CR	QR	DER	DR	ER
2018	IFRS	0.27	0.11	0.15	0.16	2.35	2.23	0.51	0.34	0.68
	HCBY	0.25	0.11	0.15	0.16	2.35	2.23	0.57	0.42	0.73
	Diffs	0.02	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.06	-0.08	-0.05
2019	IFRS	0.28	0.11	0.14	0.17	2.37	2.35	0.56	0.36	0.63
	HCBY	0.24	0.11	0.15	0.17	2.37	2.35	0.57	0.36	0.63
	Diffs	0.04	0.04	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.00	-0.00	0.00	0.00
2020	IFRS	0.29	0.11	0.15	0.16	2.67	2.65	0.46	0.31	0.68
	HCBY	0.24	0.11	0.15	0.16	2.67	2.65	0.46	0.31	0.68
	Diffs	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
2021	IFRS	0.29	0.12	0.16	0.17	2.40	2.39	0.5	0.31	0.68
	HCBY	0.25	0.12	0.16	0.18	2.40	2.39	0.46	0.31	0.68
	Diffs	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.00
2022	IFRS	0.39	0.13	0.22	0.20	2.27	2.27	0.49	0.33	0.66
	HCBY	0.28	0.13	0.18	0.20	2.27	2.27	0.5	0.33	0.66
	Diffs	0.11	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	-0.01	0.00	0.00
2023	IFRS	0.39	0.39	0.21	0.19	2.01	2.01	0.63	0.38	0.61
	HCBY	0.24	0.24	0.15	0.19	2.01	2.01	0.39	0.24	0.6
	Diffs	0.16	0.00	0.05	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.14	0.01

GPR – Gross Profit Ratio
 ROA – Return on Assets
 NPR – Net Profit Ratio
 ROE – Return on Equity
 CR – Current Ratio
 QR – Quick Ratio
 DER – Debt to Equity Ratio
 DR – Debt Ratio
 ER – Equity Ratio

Table 4 presents the results of the calculation of differences between financial ratios prepared in accordance with IFRS and NBU as of December 31, 2023. It is noted that there are no significant differences in most of the profitability and liquidity ratios, such as return on assets, return on equity, current ratio, and quick ratio. The gross profit and net profit ratios show the smallest difference between IFRS and NBU. On the other hand, solvency ratios, such as the debt-to-equity ratio and debt ratio, demonstrate slight differences in 2018 and 2023 (DER -0.06, DR -0.08 in 2018 and DER 0.24, DR 0.14 in 2023).

Discussion

One of the conclusions of the study is that according to the GCI results, the differences in financial elements in the balance sheet and income statement prepared in accordance with IFRS and NBU show minimal increases and decreases, except for certain exceptions made under NBU, such as revenue recognition, assessment and recognition of financial instruments, and investment properties. Additionally, the first implementation of IFRS (International Financial Reporting Standards) provides an opportunity to consider the book value of fixed assets in accordance with NBU. Importantly, IFRS is based on principles, while NBU is based on rules. Secondly, it was found that in most cases there are no significant differences between IFRS and NBU in calculated ratios, except for the gross value of fixed assets, profit ratios, net profit ratios, debt-to-equity ratio, and debt ratio. Finally, the overall research indicates that there is no significant difference between the financial statements prepared under IFRS and those prepared under NBU.

Taking into account the above discussions, the results of the study overall lead to the conclusion that there are no significant quantitative changes in the financial elements and financial ratios. Uzbekistan has been interested in aligning its standards with IFRS after addressing certain deviations from IFRS for several reasons, such as the existence of various legal and regulatory frameworks, government bodies, differing economic conditions within the country, differences in industry readiness, and practices in different countries. Most importantly, it also allowed for the possibility of excluding an alternative approach from IFRS. However, Uzbekistan has issued compliance standards. Thus, from this study, we can conclude that IFRS is principle-based, while NBU is rule-based. Although differences in terminology exist, no significant differences are observed between the financial statements prepared under IFRS and those prepared under NBU in accordance with the rules.

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